

SERIES REPRESENTATIONS FOR $\zeta'(2n)$ EXPRESSED IN TERMS OF ODD ZETA VALUES

JI-SUNG HA

ABSTRACT. In this paper, we derive rapidly convergent series representations for $\zeta'(2n)$ expressed in terms of odd zeta values, where the coefficients are explicitly given by the finite sum involving the Bernoulli numbers. To obtain the series representations, we introduce the functions related to the Fourier expansion of the logarithm of the gamma function.

1. INTRODUCTION

The definition of the Riemann zeta function is

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^s} \quad \text{for } \Re(s) > 1. \quad (1.1)$$

For a positive integer n , Euler established the evaluations

$$\zeta(2n) = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{(2\pi)^{2n}}{2(2n)!} B_{2n}, \quad (1.2)$$

where B_n denote the Bernoulli numbers, which are defined by

$$\frac{t}{e^t - 1} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_k}{k!} t^k.$$

Since B_n are rational and π is transcendental, it follows that $\zeta(2n)$ are transcendental numbers. In contrast, despite Apéry's proof of the irrationality of $\zeta(3)$ [1], much less is known about the arithmetic properties of $\zeta(2n+1)$. Consequently, considerable effort has been devoted to deriving various identities and series expansions for these constants. Ewell [5] investigated series representations for $\zeta(2n+1)$. Cvijovic and Klinowski [4] obtained rapidly convergent series representations for odd zeta values. Mirzoev and Safonova [7], as well as Weba [9], obtained the series representations not only for $\zeta(2n+1)$ but also for $\beta(2n)$, where $\beta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{(2k-1)^s}$ is the Dirichlet beta function. For more related results, see [8, 6].

While series representations for odd zeta values are well-developed, much less is known about series representations for $\zeta'(2n)$. In this paper, we derive new series representations for $\zeta'(2n)$ expressed in terms of odd zeta values. The coefficients appearing in these expansions are explicitly given by finite sums involving the Bernoulli numbers. These series representations converge more rapidly than the defining series

$$\zeta'(2n) = - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\log k}{k^{2n}}.$$

Key words and phrases. Riemann zeta function, rational zeta series, Bernoulli polynomials.

To obtain these series representations, we need the Bernoulli polynomials $B_n(x)$ and special functions $K_n(x)$ associated with the Fourier series of the logarithm of gamma function. Our approach is based on the integral of the product of $(B_{2n}(x) - B_{2n})K_0(x)$ on $[0, \frac{1}{2}]$. Evaluating this integral in two different ways yields the desired formulas. On the one hand, using the Laurent series expansion of $K_0(x)$ and interchanging the integration and summation yield the series involving odd zeta values. On the other hand, repeated integration by parts produces expressions containing $\zeta'(2n)$. By comparing the two evaluations, we obtain series representations for $\zeta'(2n)$ in terms of odd zeta values.

2. BERNOULLI POLYNOMIALS AND THE FUNCTIONS $K_n(x)$

The Bernoulli polynomials are defined by

$$\frac{te^{tx}}{e^t - 1} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_k(x)}{k!} t^k \quad |t| < 2\pi. \quad (2.1)$$

For $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $0 < x < 1$, the Fourier series of the Bernoulli polynomials are

$$\begin{aligned} B_{2n}(x) &= (-1)^{n+1} \frac{2(2n)!}{(2\pi)^{2n}} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos 2\pi kx}{k^{2n}} \\ B_{2n-1}(x) &= (-1)^n \frac{2(2n-1)!}{(2\pi)^{2n-1}} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin 2\pi kx}{k^{2n-1}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

The Bernoulli polynomials satisfy the properties

$$B_n(0) = B_n, \quad B'_n(x) = nB_{n-1}(x), \quad B_n(1-x) = (-1)^n B_n(x).$$

The Bernoulli polynomials can be represented by the Bernoulli numbers

$$B_n(x) = \sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} B_m x^{n-m} \quad (2.3)$$

The multiplication theorem for the Bernoulli polynomials was given by Raabe in 1851 [2, p. 30]

$$B_n(rx) = r^{n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{r-1} B_n\left(x + \frac{m}{r}\right) \quad (2.4)$$

for any positive integer r .

Motivated by the Fourier series of the Bernoulli polynomials and the Kummer's Fourier series [3], that is, for $0 < x < 1$,

$$\log \Gamma(x) = \frac{1}{2} \log \left(\frac{\pi}{\sin \pi x} \right) + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin 2\pi kx}{\pi k} (\gamma + \log 2\pi k), \quad (2.5)$$

where $\Gamma(x)$ is the gamma function, we define the functions such that for a positive integer n and $0 < x < 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} K_{2n}(x) &= (-1)^{n+1} \frac{2(2n)!}{(2\pi)^{2n}} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos 2\pi kx}{k^{2n}} (\gamma + \log 2\pi k) \\ K_{2n-1}(x) &= (-1)^n \frac{2(2n-1)!}{(2\pi)^{2n-1}} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin 2\pi kx}{k^{2n-1}} (\gamma + \log 2\pi k) \\ K_0(x) &= K_1'(x). \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

Note that for $n \geq 2$, we can define $K_n(0)$ and $K_n(1)$ since $K_n(x)$ converges absolutely for $0 \leq x \leq 1$.

Note that by (2.5),

$$K_1(x) = \frac{1}{2} \log \left(\frac{\pi}{\sin \pi x} \right) - \log \Gamma(x) \quad (2.7)$$

and

$$K_0(x) = K_1'(x) = -\frac{\pi}{2} \cot \pi x - \psi(x), \quad (2.8)$$

where $\psi(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \log \Gamma(x)$ is the digamma function.

These $K_n(x)$ functions have some similar properties with Bernoulli polynomials i.e. for a positive integer n ,

$$K_n'(x) = nK_{n-1}(x), \quad K_n(1-x) = (-1)^n K_n(x).$$

The multiplication theorem for the $K_n(x)$ is

$$K_n(rx) + B_n(rx) \log r = r^{n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{r-1} K_n \left(x + \frac{m}{r} \right) \quad (2.9)$$

for any positive integer r .

Proof. Suppose n is an even positive integer. Since

$$\sum_{m=0}^{r-1} \cos 2\pi k \left(x + \frac{m}{r} \right) = \begin{cases} r \cos 2\pi kx & r \mid k \\ 0 & r \nmid k \end{cases},$$

we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m=0}^{r-1} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos 2\pi k \left(x + \frac{m}{r} \right)}{k^n} (\gamma + \log 2\pi k) &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\gamma + \log 2\pi k}{k^n} \sum_{m=0}^{r-1} \cos 2\pi k \left(x + \frac{m}{r} \right) \\ &= r \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos 2\pi rlx}{(rl)^n} (\gamma + \log 2\pi rl) \\ &= r^{1-n} \left(\sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos 2\pi lrx}{l^n} (\gamma + \log 2\pi l) + \log r \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos 2\pi lrx}{l^n} \right). \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore K_n(rx) + B_{2n}(x) \log r = r^{n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{r-1} K_n \left(x + \frac{m}{r} \right)$$

Similarly, we obtain (2.9) for an odd integer n . □

3. SERIES REPRESENTATION FOR $\zeta'(2n)$

Theorem 3.1. For $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $0 < x < 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta'(2n) &= \frac{(-1)^{n+1} \pi^{2n}}{2(2n)!} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{2n-1} \binom{2n}{m} \frac{2^m B_m}{2k+2n-m+1} \zeta(2k+1) \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{2k} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \sum_{m=0}^{2n-1} \binom{2n}{m} \frac{2^m B_m}{2n-m} + 2^{2n} B_{2n} \log 2\pi \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

Proof. Since for $0 < x < 1$,

$$-\pi \cot \pi x = 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \zeta(2k) x^{2k-1} - \frac{1}{x} \quad (3.2)$$

and

$$\psi(x) = - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \zeta(k) (-x)^{k-1} - \frac{1}{x} - \gamma, \quad (3.3)$$

by (2.8), we obtain

$$K_0(x) = -\frac{\pi}{2} \cot \pi x - \psi(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \zeta(2k+1) x^{2k} + \frac{1}{2x} + \gamma. \quad (3.4)$$

Since $K_0(x)$ converges uniformly, by Fubini's theorem, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} (B_{2n}(y) - B_{2n}) K_0(y) dy \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \zeta(2k+1) \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} (B_{2n}(y) - B_{2n}) y^{2k} dy + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} (B_{2n}(y) - B_{2n}) \frac{1}{y} dy \\ &\quad + \gamma \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} (B_{2n}(y) - B_{2n}) dy \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \zeta(2k+1) \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \sum_{m=0}^{2n-1} \binom{2n}{m} B_m y^{2k+2n-m} dy \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \sum_{m=0}^{2n-1} \binom{2n}{m} B_m y^{2n-m-1} dy - \frac{\gamma}{2} B_{2n} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \zeta(2k+1) \sum_{m=0}^{2n-1} \binom{2n}{m} \frac{B_m}{2k+2n-m+1} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{2k+2n-m+1} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{m=0}^{2n-1} \binom{2n}{m} \frac{B_m}{2n-m} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{2n-m} - \frac{\gamma}{2} B_{2n} \end{aligned}$$

And since for $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\begin{aligned} B_{2n-1}(0) &= 0 \quad \text{for } n \neq 1, \quad B_1(0) = -\frac{1}{2}, \\ B_{2n-1}\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) &= K_{2n-1}(0) = K_{2n-1}\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = 0, \\ K_{2n}(0) &= (-1)^{n+1} \frac{2(2n)!}{(2\pi)^{2n}} ((\gamma + \log 2\pi)\zeta(2n) - \zeta'(2n)) \end{aligned}$$

by using integration by parts, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} (B_{2n}(y) - B_{2n})K_0(y) dy &= -2n \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} B_{2n-1}(y)K_1(y) dy \\ &= \frac{2n(2n-1)}{2} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} B_{2n-2}(y)K_2(y) dy \\ &= \dots = -\frac{1}{2} K_{2n}(0) = (-1)^n \frac{(2n)!}{(2\pi)^{2n}} ((\gamma + \log 2\pi)\zeta(2n) - \zeta'(2n)). \end{aligned}$$

By combining two results and (1.2), we obtain (3.1). \square

Example 3.2.

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta'(2) &= -\frac{\pi^2}{4} \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(n+2)\zeta(2n+1)}{(n+1)(2n+3)2^{2n}} - \frac{2}{3} \log 2\pi + \frac{3}{2} \right) \\ \zeta'(4) &= -\frac{\pi^4}{48} \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2n^2 + 11n + 16)\zeta(2n+1)}{(n+2)(2n+3)(2n+5)2^{2n}} - \frac{48}{90} \log 2\pi + \frac{11}{12} \right) \\ \zeta'(6) &= -\frac{\pi^6}{1440} \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(12n^3 + 120n^2 + 409n + 480)\zeta(2n+1)}{(n+3)(2n+3)(2n+5)(2n+7)2^{2n}} - \frac{32}{21} \log 2\pi + \frac{38}{15} \right). \end{aligned}$$

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Apéry. Irrationalité de $\zeta(2)$ et $\zeta(3)$. *Astérisque*, 61(11-13):1, 1979.
- [2] H. Bateman and A. Erdélyi. Higher transcendental functions, volume ii. *Bateman Manuscript Project) Mc Graw-Hill Book Company*, 410, 1953.
- [3] B. C. Berndt. The gamma function and the hurwitz zeta-function. *The American Mathematical Monthly*, 92(2):126–130, 1985.
- [4] D. Cvijovic and J. Klinowski. New rapidly convergent series representations for $\zeta(2n+1)$. *Proceedings of the American Mathematical Society*, 125(5):1263–1271, 1997.
- [5] J. A. Ewell. On the zeta function values $\zeta(2k+1)$, $k=1, 2, \dots$. *The Rocky Mountain Journal of Mathematics*, pages 1003–1012, 1995.
- [6] C. Lupu and D. Orr. Series representations for the apéry constant $\zeta(3)$ involving the values $\zeta(2n)$. *The Ramanujan Journal*, 48(3):477–494, 2019.
- [7] K. Mirzoev. Representations of and related numbers in the form of definite integrals and rapidly convergent series. In *Doklady Mathematics*, volume 102, pages 396–400. Springer, 2020.
- [8] H. Srivastava. Some families of rapidly convergent series representations for the zeta functions. *Taiwanese Journal of Mathematics*, 4(4):569–598, 2000.
- [9] M. Weba. Series representations and asymptotically finite representations for the numbers $\zeta(2m+1)$ and $\beta(2m)$. *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications*, 514(2):126330, 2022.

Email address: jsha57721@gmail.com